

THE ROLE OF MOTIVATION IN TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE AT SULU STATE COLLEGE

Imelda A. Paraja

Sulu State College, Graduate Studies, Capitol Site, Jolo, Sulu, Philippines, 7400

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8120060>

Published Date: 06-July-2023

Abstract: This study ascertained the extent and the significant difference between the role of motivation in teaching and learning English as a second language as perceived by teachers and students at Sulu State College when data are grouped according to student gender, course, average monthly family income, and teaches gender, educational attainment, and length of service. It answered the following research questions on the following hypothesis: There is no significant difference in teachers and students perceptions towards the role of motivation in in teaching and learning English as a Second Language in Sulu State College when data are grouped according to each of the following students socio-demographic profile: gender, course and average monthly family income; and teachers socio-demographic profile: gender, educational attainment; and length of service. Descriptive quantitative research design with 110 students and 12 English Language Teacher at Sulu State College was employed. The mean percentage score and standards deviation were used to determine the extent off teachers and students perceptions on the role of motivation. Test for independent samples and One-way ANOVA were used to determine the significant differences in the perceptions of teachers and students in the role of motivation in teaching and learning English as a Second Language.

Keywords: average monthly family income, educational attainment, course, gender, length of service, socio-demographic profile.

I. INTRODUCTION

A Popular saying state that "You can lead a horse to water, but you can't make him drink" When applied to English language teaching, and learning situation, this would imply that the school can pool students in the classroom where teacher may provide them plenty of language inputs, but the student may not learn them due to some reasons. This is simply to say that language learning, much like any other type of learning activities in some academic disciplines is being influenced by several factors. That is motivation has been perceived as one from among the prominent driving forces in most successful language learning endeavor.

Sultana (2014) stressed that motivation plays a significant role in the rate and success of second and foreign language in general, and in classroom language learning in particular. It "provides the primary impetuous to initiate learning the second language and later the driving force to sustain the long and often tedious learning process. (Dornyei, 1998, p.117). Motivation, however, is "a complex" and "multifaceted contract. (Gardner, J 985; Williams & Burdoen, 1997). It consist of such factors as theattached value of a task, the rate of success expected by leaners, whether learners believe they are competent enough to succeed, and what they think to be the reason for their success or failure at the task (Dornyei & Ushioda, 2011).

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 10, Issue 4, pp: (30-38), Month: July - August 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

However, motivating learners to develop in the target language is acknowledged to be a complex process. In many instances, students face many obstacles in learning English and are often demotivated to learn. However, certain motivational strategies, identified by research on motivation, can help learner adopt more positive attitudes towards language learning.

In second language learning the most recognized social-psychological variable is motivation that plays the key role. According to Gardner (1985) the term "motivation" means 'referring to the extent to which the individual works to learn the language because of a desire to do so and the satisfaction experienced in this activity (p.10).

Although motivation has been inevitably appreciated as a strong driving force in language learning, its intensity may vary according to type of learning environment that may include the educational level, academic discipline, students, teachers and etc. In the words, the extent of role of motivation in relation to these variables need to be called so as to guide educator in the ways they shall deal with learners with varied individual learning difference.

Since today's learners want English Language Teaching to be customized according to their needs, a study that will determine the role of motivation in college instruction is much relevant at present. Hence, the study was conducted to gather empirical data among Sulu State College student as basis in confirming or denying the aforementioned claim.

II. RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

Studies and research work related to the role of motivation in Teaching and Learning process are reviewed in this chapter.

International Studies

Sultana (2014) conducted study on " The Role of Motivation in Teaching and Learning English as a Second Language at the Secondary level. National/Local Studies which aimed at exploring whether motivation can make the ESL classes more effective or not. This research was carried out to verify that in Bangladesh, motivation can become an effective tool in teaching and learning English as a Second language. Motivation is one of the characteristics of the Language learning and teaching and it is a helpful facilitator in the Language Learning process. It also aimed to discuss the major theories of motivation and how teachers can influence learner's motivation. It also aimed to explain how teachers can generate and maintain motivation in their teaching process. In order to conduct this research the researcher interviewed some teachers and students of private English Medium School & College and three teachers of a Private University. Dhaka, Bangladesh, and the results revealed that motivation is an effective factor in teaching and learning English as a Second language at the secondary level in the context of Bangladesh.

Al- Ghamdi, Ahmed M. (2014) carried out a study on the Role of Motivation as a single Factor in Second Language Learning which aimed to investigate the various aspects and models of motivation that affect Second Language Learning (SLL). The primary focus is on the learner and the internal factors that encourage and facilitate their pursuit of language achievement (i.e. intrinsic/integrative). It is evident that there are external factors that also influence this process (i.e. extrinsic/instrumental). So, the significant question such as: whether one can identify which type of motivation an individual will exhibit and whether this will lead to a greater success than another type, are also addressed in this paper. In line with William and Burden (1997), Motivation from both internal and external influences are to some extent and rooted within individuals. However, with that being said, a common and among scholars who may have opposing views in this topic, would agree that the individual themselves are or should be aware of the motivation that drive them in second language acquisition.

III. METHOD: RESEARCH BLUEPRINT

This chapter deals with the research method that was adopted in the conduct of this study. It deals with research method design, locale, and respondent of the study, sampling design data gathering procedure, research instrument and statistical treatments of data.

Research Design

A research design is "a program that guides a researcher in collecting, analyzing and interpreting observed facts (Bless and Higson-Smith, 1995 p.63). Similarly, Babble and Monton (2001: p.75) regard research design as a roadway or blueprint by which one intends to conduct a research and achieve his/her research goals and objectives" A descriptive research design thought a quantitative research method was employed in this study, i.e. with purport to describe, quantify, and infer the

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 10, Issue 4, pp: (30-38), Month: July - August 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

phenomenon of teachers and students perceptions on the role motivation in English language teaching and learning process, and the significant difference in this variable when data are group d according to gender, age, parents average monthly income , educational attainment, and length of service.

Teachers and students at Sulu State College are the main source of data which were quantify d and treated with appropriate statistical tools to answer the research questions in this study. Library and internet research were the sources of information that were used as bases to structure; and enrich the theoretical and conceptual framework of this research. Questionnaire on Teachersand Student's Perceptions on Role of Motivation were the main instrument used in collecting data from the respondent that were used in this study.

Research Locale

This study was conducted at Sulu State College among English language teachers and students. Jolo is the capital town of Sulu province where Sulu State College is situated.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were the English teacher and students at Sulu State College, Jolo, Sulu Specially, respondents that were included in this study are the students and English teacher prorated at the different department namely: School of Arts and Sciences, School o Nursing. At least one hundred ten (110) students with 34 male and 76 female and all college English teachers were used as representative samples. The table below shows the distribution of the target samples of this study.

Distribution of samples according to School and Gender

Academic departments/Schools	Students			Teachers		
	Gender			Gender		
School of Arts and Sciences	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
School of Business Administration				5	7	12
School of Computer Science and Engineering	4	18	22			
School of Education	11	11	22			
School of Nursing	8	14	22			
School of Education	11	11	22			
School of Nursing	0	22	22			
Total	34	76	110	5	7	12

Sampling Design

A none-probability sampling method through purposive sampling procedure was employed in this study. That is, availability and time constrains, representative samples from school of arts and Sciences. School of Business Administration, School of Computer Science and Engineering, School of Education, School of Nursing were purposively chosen as sample of this study. The use of purposive sampling procedure was to ensure the collection of desired quality and quantity of data that were used in this study.

Data Gathering procedure

In collection of data, the study has applied the following steps

- 1) A permit to administer the questioner was sought from the Dean of the Graduate Studies of the Sulu State College and then from the Office of the College President as well from the Deans of the five academic departments, and
- 2) The launching and administering as well as the retrieval of the questionnaire conducted personally by the researcher.

Research Instrument

A self-report questionnaire was the main instrument used to gather data on demographic profiles, teachers and students perceptions on the role of motivation in English Language Learning and Teaching process at Sulu State College. The questionnaires on Teachers and students perceptions on the role of motivation in English language teaching and learning process were patterned and adapted from Sultana (2014) Questionnaire

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 10, Issue 4, pp: (30-38), Month: July - August 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

There are two parts of each of the researcher instrument used in this study. First of the questionnaire focused on obtaining the socio-demographic profiles of the respondent which include; gender, age, average monthly family income, educational attainment, and year of teaching experience. The second part dealt with the collection of data on teachers and students perceptions of motivations in English language teaching and learning process.

Validity and Reliability

The instrument that was used in this research patterned and adapted from Sultana (2014) Questionnaires on Teachers and Students perception of the role of motivation in teaching and learning process. These standardized questionnaires were already used in Sultana’s (2014) study thus their validity and reliability are already establish. However to suit its applicability with the present study, this was subjected for perusal of at least two expert from among the faculty members from the Schools of Graduate Studies of the Sulu State College.

Statistical Treatment

Both descriptive and inferential statistical tool were employed in the treatments of data gathered for this study namely:

- 1) Mean, Percentages and standards deviation were employed to determine the following: the socio-demographic profile of students and teachers in terms of gender, age average monthly family income; educational attainment, length of service and role of motivation;
- 2) *t*-test for independent samples was employed to determine the significant differences in both teachers and students perceptions on the role of motivation when data are grouped according to gender and age; and
- 3) One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed to determine the significant differences in both teachers and students perception on the role of motivation when data are grouped according to average monthly income; educational attainment and length of service.

Scoring of Responses

The following ranges and verbal interpretations were used to score the responses in the items of the questionnaires.

Options	Scale Range	Verbal Interpretations
5	4.50	Strongly Agree
4	3.50	Agree
3	2.50	Undecided
2	1.50	Disagree
1	1.50	Strongly Disagree

To determine the level of motivation, the following scale was used:

Options	Scale Range	Verbal Interpretations	Level of Motivation
5	4.50	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Motivated
4	3.50	Agree	Highly Motivated
3	2.50	Undecided	Motivated
2	1.50	Disagree	Slightly Motivated
1	1.50	Strongly Disagree	Not at All Motivated

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the presentations, analyses and interpretations of results based on the data obtained for this study. It also deals specifically with student’s socio-demographic profile in terms of gender, course and average monthly family income; and English language teachers socio-demographic profile in terms of gender, educational attainment and length service at Sulu State College; the extent of students and teachers perception toward the role of motivation in teaching and learning English as a second language; and significant differences in teachers and students perceptions towards the role of motivations I teaching and learning English when data are grouped according to each of the following: students socio-demographic profile: gender; course; and average monthly family income ; and teachers socio-demographic profile : gender; educational attainment; and length of service

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

 Vol. 10, Issue 4, pp: (30-38), Month: July - August 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Based on the proper, coring and statistical treatment of data gathered for this study, the following are the presentations, analyses and interpretation of results which correspond to each of the research questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of college student at Sulu State College in terms of each of the following categories:

1.1. Gender;

1.2. Course; and

1.3. Average monthly family income?

Table 1.1 presents the demographic profile of students in terms gender. It can be gleaned from this table that out of 110 students-respondents of Sulu State College, 34 are male 76 are female. This means that College Students pre-dominate their male counterparts. In contrary, Wimolmas (2012) study reported that out of a total of 30 respondents, the majority of respondents were male (76.7%) and the minority of the respondents were female (23.3%).

Table 1.1 Demographic profile of students in terms of Gender

Gender	Number of Students	Percent
Male	34	30.90
Female	76	69.09
Total	110	100.00

Table 1.2 shows the demographic profile of students in terms of course they are enrollee at the Sulu State College. In this table, each course is composed of 32 students taken as representative sample. This means that, in this study, each academic course is equally represented.

Table 1.2 Demographic Profile of students in terms of Course.

Course	Number of Students	Percent
AB	32	29.01
BSE/BEE	32	29.01
BSBA	32	29.01
BSIT/BSCS/BSCOE	32	29.01
BSN	32	29.01
Total	110	100.00

Table 1.3 deals with the demographic profile of students in terms of average monthly family income. It can be seen on this table that 71 out of 110 students whose family income ranges from 5,000 thousand and below. This is followed by 24 students with 5,100 to 10,000; and 5 students each for 11,100 to 15, 000, 15,100 to 20,000 and 21,000 and above. This means that the students-respondents in this study are mostly connected at the lowest family income level.

Table 1.3

Average monthly family income	Number of Students	Percent
5,000 and below	71	64.55
5,100 to 10,000	24	21.81
11,100 to 15,000	5	4.55
15,100 to 20,000	5	4.55
21,000 and above	5	4.55
Total	110	100.00

2. What is the socio-demographic profile of English language teachers at Sulu State College in each of the following categories:

2.1. Gender;

2.2. Educational attainment; and

2.3. Length of Service?

Table 2.1 shows the demographic profile of teachers in terms of gender. Five are male which is 41.66% and 7 are female which is 58.33% of the total of 12 teacher-respondents. This means that female out-numbered the male English language teaching force at Sulu State College.

Table 2.1 Demographic Profile of teachers in terms of Gender

Gender	Number of Students	Percent
Male	5	41.66
Female	7	58.33
Total	12	100.00

In Table 2.2 which presents the demographic profile of teachers in terms of educational attainment, it can be seen that 5 respondents which constitutes 41.66% each represents AB/BS OR AB/BS plus units in master’s program and Full-pledged Ed. /Ph.D. Only 2 or 16.66% of English language teachers at Sulu State College have obtained Full-pledged MA/MS degree. This means that bachelor degree holders are being allowed to teach in English language teaching program of the college.

Tab! 2.2 Demographic Profile of teacher in term of Educational attainment

Educational Attainment	Number of Teachers	Percent
AB/BS or AB/BS plus units in master’s program	5	41.66
Full-pledged MA/MS	2	16.66
MA/MS plus doctoral units	0	0
Full-pledge Ed.D./Ph.D	5	41.66
Total	12	100.00

Table 2.3 deals with the demographic profile of teacher in terms of length of service. There are 5 which is 41.66% out of 12 Teacher-respondents who have 2 years and below of length of service. However, 7 of them who have been in teaching English language for at least 10 years and above. None of the respondents who have 3 to 9 years of teaching experience in the college. This means that as there are more veteran teachers, there exist also a considerable number of neophytes to the English language teaching force of the Sulu State College.

Table 2.3

Length of Service	Number of teachers	Percent
2 years and below	5	41.66
3 to 5 years	0	0
6 to 9 years	0	0
10 years and above	7	58.33
Total	12	100.00

3. What I the extent of teachers and students perceptions towards the role of motivation in teaching and learning English as a Second Language at Sulu State College?

3.1. Students’ perceptions

Table shows students' perceptions toward the role of motivation in teaching and learning English as a second language. With the mean score of 3.406 and standard deviation of .38821, generally the student-respondents *Agree* on the issue that motivation plays an important role in teaching and learning English as a second language at Sulu State College.

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 10, Issue 4, pp: (30-38), Month: July - August 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Moreover the item "Motivation in the English language classes is good for the students" obtained a mean score of 4.5636 with standard deviation of .71070 which is rated a *Strongly Agree*. Item number such as 1, 2, 5, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 19 and 20 are rated as *Agree* while 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11 and 18 are rated as *Undecided*. This means that the student-respondents do consider motivation, which plays a crucial role as an important factor in teaching and learning English situations.

Matsumoto (2011) stated that student proficiency in using a language and the succeeding level of fluency they may have are influenced by motivation. And this motivation, according to Matsumoto can be directly influenced by the teachers. Thus, it can be implied from the study that learner may not be autonomy-driven as they need the mentoring of the teachers when the former learn a language.

Xiao (2012) stated that learning difficulties will be lessened if motivation is fortified by the teacher through various conditioning and strategies. Also, language aptitude and learning conditions are both determined by motivation, and motivation can be highly encouraged if the teachers are incorporating the appropriate techniques in heightening the student interest in language learning.

V. CONCLUSION

The following are the conclusions made based on the findings of this study:

1. Generally, both students and teachers of English language agree that motivation plays a vital role in teaching and learning English as a Second Language in Sulu State College;
2. Students belong to the highest level of average monthly family income (21,100 thousand & above) have a better level of discrimination than those in the lower bracket with regards to ease in judging the role of motivation in teaching and learning English as a Second Language; and that gender and course do not affect their perceptions;
3. Teacher's length of service, unlike gender and educational attainment, this variable proportionately affects their perceptions toward the role of motivation in teaching and learning English as a Second Language in Sulu State College, that is, the longer the teacher in service, the higher his ability to perceive the role of motivation; and
4. This study supports Gardner's (1985) Model of Motivation in which he states that motivation is a combination of effort plus desire to achieve the goal of learning the language plus favorable attitudes towards learning the language. It further supports Gardner's claim that students are more inclined to instrumental motivation, vis-a-vis refers to more functional reasons for learning the language such as getting a better job, a higher salary, or passing an examination.

VI. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of this research, the following are recommended:

1. English language teachers must promote students' awareness toward learning process; and keep learners in touch with modern English language teaching methods.
2. The effect of motivation on academic achievement and language proficiency among college students should be considered;
3. A language club should be organized and established in every academic department of the college since this could help develop the learners' English language skill.
4. Teachers should introduce "a paradigm shift", that is, they should motivate students to change their mentality from aiming only at passing the English examinations somehow to development of language proficiency;
5. All instructional materials like English textbooks should be redesigned so that language learning becomes fun and activities must be fully related to our real life.
6. The school must provide the necessary training and seminars to update the teachers on skills relevant to the changing curriculum to ensure improved English instruction.
7. English teachers should develop the interest to use their resourcefulness and creativity to make English lessons enjoyable to the student.

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

 Vol. 10, Issue 4, pp: (30-38), Month: July - August 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

8. Teachers should manifest sensitivity and concern for their students' competence in English especially in literary genres and language itself.
9. The school heads should work with the teacher and parents to lessen the effects of some issues brought upon by the demotivating factors that affect the English instruction; and
10. Researchers in the field of education are encouraged to conduct the same study but different in setting. This is suggested for constant research in education leads to enhancement teachers' pedagogical knowledge and skills.

REFERENCES
BOOKS

- [1] Baker, Therese L (1999). *Doing Social Research*. New York: McGraw-Hill Companies, Inc. Daleon. Sixto O. et al. (1989). *Fundamentals of Statistics*. Philippines: National Book Store. Inc.
- [2] Downie. N.M. and Heath. R.W. (1984). *Basic Statistical Methods*. Philippines: Harper and Row Publishing, Inc.
- [3] Fraenkel. Jack R. & Wallen. Norman E. (2003). *How to Design and Evaluate Research in Education*. 5th Edition. New York: McGraw-Hill Companies, Inc.
- [4] Greenacre. Michael (2007). *Interdisciplinary Statistics: CORRESPONDENCE ANALYSIS in PRACTICE*. Second Edition. New York: Copyright 2007 by Taylor & Francis Group. LLC. Chapman & Hall/CRC
- [5] Jackson. Sherri L. (2009). *Research Methods and Statistics: A Critical Thinking Approach*. Belmont. CA USA: Wadsworth, 10 Davis Drive, library of Congress Control Number: 2008920909. ISBN-13: 978-0-495-51001-7, ISBN-10: 0-495-51001-7.
- [6] Larson-Hall, Jenifer (2010). *A Guide to Doing Statistics in Second Language Research Using SPSS*. (2010 Taylor & Francis. www.eBookstore.tandf.co.uk.
- [7] Oakes, Michael P. (1998). *Statistics for Corpus Linguistics* Edinburgh Textbooks in Empirical Linguistics. Edinburgh University Press.
- [8] Ott. Lyman R. (2001). *An Introduction to Statistical Methods and Data Analysis*. Fifth Edition. COPYRIGHT Wadsworth Group. Pacific Grove, 511 Forest Lodge Road CA 93950 USA: DUXBURY
- [9] Ramchand, Gillian and Dreiss, Charles (2007). *The Oxford Handbook of LINGUISTIC INTERFACES*: OXFORD. University Press.
- [10] Ross. Sheldon M. (2010). *Introduction Statistics*. Third Edition. 30 Corporate Drive, Suite 400, Burlington, MA 01803. USA: Academic Press.

JOURNALS

- [11] Alaga, Nathalie Ann C. (2016). *Motivation and Attitude of Students towards Learning English Language*. International Conference on Research in Social Sciences. Humanities and Education (SSHE-2016) May 20-21, 2016 Cebu (Philippines)
- [12] Al Othman, Fadel H.M. & Shuqair, Khaled M. (2013). *The Impact of Motivation on English Language Learning in the Gulf States*. International Journal of Higher Education: Vol.2 No. 4.2013
- [13] Aquino, Aleejah Caitlin et al. (2016). *Demotivating Factors in Learning the English Language*. Presented at the DLSU Research Congress 2016 De La Salle University, Manila, Philippines March 7-9, 2016
- [14] Binalet, Cedra B. and Guerra July M. (2014). *A Study on the Relationship between Motivation and Language Learning Achievement among Tertiary Students*. International Journal of Applied Linguistics & English Literature ISSN 2200-3592 (Print), ISSN 2200-3452 (Online); Vol.3 No.5; September 2014
- [15] Cabansag, John N. (2013) *the Attitudinal Propensity of Students Towards Strategies in English Language Learning*. International Referred Research Journal; www.researchesworld.com; Vol-IV, Issue-2, April 2013 [10]

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and LearningVol. 10, Issue 4, pp: (30-38), Month: July - August 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

- [16] Gomari, Hamid and Lucas, Rochelle Irene (2103). Foreign Language Learning Motivation and Anxiety among Iranian Students on the Philippines. *Philippines ESL Journal*, Vol 10, February 2013
- [17] Mante-Estacio, Ma. Joahana (2012). Dimensions of Reading Motivation among Filipino Bilinguals. *TESOL Journal* Vol.7,pp. 10-29 @2012 <http://www.tesol-journal.com>
- [18] Martinez, Diego Uribe et al. (2013). Attitude of Mexican American Students Towards Learning English as a Second Language in a Structured Immersion Program *Porta Linguarum* 20, Junio 2013
- [19] Paran, Gracia and Tibli, Puraida (2019). Perceived Parental Encouragement, Motivation and Attitudes Towards Learning English Language Among Tertiary Students *Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference of Teaching and Learning (ICTL 2009) INTI University College, Malaysia*
- [20] Schmidt, Richard and Watanabe, Yuichi (2001). Motivation, Strategy Use, and pedagogical Preference in Foreign Language Learning in Z. Dornyei & R. Schmidt (Eds), *Motivation and second Language acquisition (Technical Report #23, pp.313-3590. Honolulu; University of Hawaii, Second Language Teaching and Curriculum Center.*
- [21] Setiyadi, Ag Bambang and Sukirlan, Muhammad (2014) Language and Motivation of the Islamic School Students: How Madrasa Students of the Academic Year 2013-2014 in Indonesia Perceive English, English Teaching and Learning and Native Speakers of English *Pertanika J. Soc. Sci & Hum.* 24 (1)
- [22] Shirbagi, Naser (2010). An Exploration of Undergraduate students' Motivation and Attitudes towards English Language Acquisition. *Journal of Behavioral Sciences* Vol.20, Number 2, 2010
- [23] Siregar, Fenty I (2010). The Language Attitudes of Students of English Literature and D3 English at Maranatha Christian University towards American English, British English and Englishes in Southeast Asia, and their various Contexts of use in Indonesia. *Philippines ESL Journal*, Vol. 4, February 2010
- [24] Sultana, Mosha Afroza (2014). The Role of Motivation in Teaching and Learning English as a Second Language at the Secondary Level Language in India www.languageinindia.com 14:5 May 2014
- [25] Tsuda, Sanae (2003). Attitudes towards English Language Learning in Higher Education in Japan (2); Raising Awareness of the Nation of Global English. *Intercultural Communication Studies* XII-3 2003
- [26] Youssef, Awad Mohammad S. (2012) Role of Motivation and Attitude in Introduction and Learning of English as a Foreign Language in Libyan High Schools. *International Journal of Linguistic* ISSN 1948-5425: 2012, Vol 4, No. 2